

CHEMOTHERAPEUTIC DYES: SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED AMINOPHENOXAZINES

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Several 5- β -hydroxyethylamino-9-di(mono)alkylaminobenzo(a)phenoxazines and phenyl or *tert.*-butylaminophenoxazines have been prepared as potential tumor inhibiting and antitubercular agents.

The basic dyes, Nile Blue A and Nile Blue 2B, containing a benzo (a) phenoxazonium nucleus, have been found to possess a selective tumor staining and growth retarding action (Lewis *et al.*, *Anat. Record*, 1946, **95**, 89; 1946, **98**, 201; 1947, **99**, 369), and as such are of potential importance as diagnostic and therapeutic agents in the study of cancer. New methylene blue GG, a phenoxazine derivative, was found (de Witts, *J. Inf. Dis.*, 1913, **13**, 378) to stain tubercle bacillus *in vitro* and penetrate the tubercle *in vivo*. These findings led Okamoto (*Jap. Med. J.*, 1948, 1422; *Chem. Abs.*, 1951, **45**, 5757), Crossley *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 573; *Chem. Abs.*, 1955, 2085), and Clapp *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*; 1952, **74**, 1939) to synthesise derivatives of phenoxazines, with a view to studying the effects of structural modifications on these actions, and the toxicity of the compound to the host.

Crossley *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) studied three series of these compounds, viz., (a) 5-alkylamino-9-alkylamino-, (b) 5-arylamino-9-dialkylamino-, and (c) 5-heterocyclic amino-9-dialkylamino-benzo(a)phenoxazines and found that the compounds of the second series were of the greatest importance, whilst those of the first series possessed some activity, and those of the third were without significant activity.

Clapp *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) extended this work by synthesising aminobenzo(a) phenoxazines containing (i) a methyl group in position-6, (ii) a chlorine atom in position-10, (iii) 5-arylamino-9-arylamino groupings, and found that the substitution in 6 and 10 positions always lowered the activity of the parent compound; removal of the benzo ring or of 9-dialkylamino substituent also resulted in the lowering of the activity.

The present work was undertaken to study other variations in the structure of these dyes.

The difference in the potency of therapeutically active compounds of varying fat/water solubility coefficients arises out of the difference in the distribution of the drug between the aqueous phase of the tissue fluids, through which the drug must pass to reach the site of infection, and the infected tissues in which the drug molecules combine with bioreceptors. Since the cell membrane of mycobacteria and to some extent the tissues that harbour them are rich in lipid material, the drug should also possess sufficient lipid solubility so as to pass through these tissues and kill the bacteria. For this purpose, benzo(a)phenoxazines, having alkylamino groups for lipid solubility in position-9 and a β -hydroxyethylamino grouping in position-5, were synthesised to confer partial water solubility.

In addition to these, some simple aminophenoxazines with phenyl and *tert.*-butyl substituents have been prepared as the investigations of Boothroyd *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1499) have established that 1-amino- and 3-aminophenoxazines possess marked tuberculostatic activity.

5- β -Hydroxyethylamino-9-dialkylamino-benzo(a)phenoxazonium chlorides have been prepared by the following reaction :

[I: R = R' = Me. II: R = Et; R' = H. III: R = R' = Pr. IV: R = R' = C₆H₅.
V: R = R' = C₆H₁₁. VI: R = R' = C₆H₁₃.]

Of these dyes, (IV) and (V) could not be isolated from the final reaction mixture which was in the form of a dark green syrup and as such could not be characterised. Other dyes were quite similar to 5-alkylamino-9-dialkylamino-benzo(a)phenoxazonium chlorides (Crossley *et al.*, *loc. cit.*), being dark green crystalline solids which imparted blue colour in acidic medium and red colour in basic medium, which is the characteristic of the series. They also formed precipitates with silver nitrate solution. These dyes, for most part, did not show satisfactory melting or decomposition points, and hence, were characterised as picrates which could easily be obtained in the pure state.

α -Naphthyl-(N- β -hydroxyethyl)-amine, (A), required in the above condensation, was prepared from α -naphthylamine by a method analogous to one adopted by Nityanand *et al.* (*J. Sch. Ind. Res.*, 1954, 18B, 260) for the syntheses of *p*-(ω -hydroxy-alkylamino)-*p*-aminodiphenylsulphones.

The necessary 3-monoalkyl- and 3-dialkylaminophenols were prepared from 3-aminophenols by alkylation with appropriate alkyl iodide. They were converted into the corresponding 5-mono- and dialkylamino-2-nitrosophenol hydrochlorides (B) by the same technique as described by Crossley *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

The benzo(a)phenoxazonium salts were prepared by the condensation of (A) and (B) in absolute alcohol medium instead of ordinary alcohol because of the hydrophilic grouping in (A), following the method A of Crossley *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

Picrates of these dyes were prepared from the free bases as recorded in the Experimental.

The aminophenoxazines were prepared by the catalytic reduction of the nitrophenoxazines using Adams' catalyst and acetic acid. The bases were isolated in their oxidised form as imine hydrochlorides. The absence of amino groups was indicated by the inability to form a diazo compound. Purification of these dyes by reprecipitation or recrystallisation failed to remove a small amount of water-insoluble material. As such they were also characterised through their picrates.

The four nitrophenoxazines were obtained by the condensation of *o*-aminophenol with 2-chloro-3:5-dinitrodiphenyl, 4-chloro-3:5-dinitrodiphenyl, 4-chloro-3:5:4'-trinitrodiphenyl and 4-chloro-3:5-dinitro-1-*tert.*-butylbenzene respectively, as represented below:

The chloro compounds were obtained from the corresponding nitrophenols and phosphorus oxychloride in presence of diethylaniline.

3:5-Dinitro-2-oxydiphenyl (Borsche, *Annalen.*, 1900, 312, 226), 3:5-dinitro-4-oxydiphenyl (Latschinoff, *Ber.*, 1873, 6, 195), 3:5:4'-trinitro-4-oxydiphenyl (Garcia Banus *et al.*, *Anal. Fis. Quim.*, 1923, 126) and 3:5-dinitro-4-oxy-*tert.*-butylbenzene (Arthuestüder, *Annalen*, 1882, 211, 244), needed in the above preparations, were obtained by the nitration of *o*- and *p*-diphenyls and *p*-*tert.*-butylphenol respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aminobenzo(a)phenoxazines

α-Naphthyl(*N*-tosyl)amine was prepared by an improved method other than the one reported by Witt and Schemitt (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2371). *α*-Naphthylamine (1 *M*) was dissolved in the minimum amount of pyridine and *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (1 *M*) was added to it. The mixture after being refluxed for 20 minutes was poured over crushed ice and washed with an excess of water. The solid obtained was recrystallised from a mixture of glacial acetic acid and water, m.p. 157°, yield theoretical. Witt *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) report the same m.p.

α-Naphthyl (*N*-tosyl-*N*-*β*-hydroxyethyl)amine.—The tosylated compound (18 g.) was dissolved in 80 c.c. of ethyleneglycol in a 250 c.c. round bottomed flask and a 20% KOH solution (50 c.c.) added. After adding 24 c.c. of ethylene chlorohydrin to the mixture, the flask was sealed and heated in a steam-bath for 8 hours. The flask was then cooled and the contents poured over ice. The pink, plastic-like mass solidified on

cooling and on rubbing with a few drops of alcohol. On recrystallisation from alcohol pinkish crystals were obtained, m.p. 108°, yield 18 g. (Found: N, 3.92. $C_{17}H_{19}O_4NS$ requires N, 4.11 per cent).

2-Naphthyl (N-β-acetoxyethyl-N-tosyl) amine was obtained by refluxing the hydroxy compound (16 g.), dissolved in 25 c.c. of pyridine, with 36 c.c. of acetic anhydride for half an hour. The reaction mixture was poured over ice and washed with an excess of ice water. The oily residue solidified after about 2 hours' cooling. It was then recrystallised from alcohol in lustrous pinkish needles, m.p. 92°, yield 24 g. (Found: N, 4.02. $C_{21}H_{21}O_4NS$ requires N, 3.65 per cent).

2-Naphthyl(N-β-hydroxyethyl)amine.—Detosylation and deacetylation of the above compound was simultaneously effected by heating the compound (20 g.) with HCl (conc., 36 c.c.) and 50 c.c. of alcohol in a sealed vessel at 100° for 8 hours. The cooled solution was made alkaline with ammonium hydroxide and the crude reaction product recrystallised from alcohol as light pink crystals, m.p. 122°, yield 15.5 g. (Found: N, 7.15. $C_{12}H_{13}ON$ requires N, 7.49 per cent).

Dialkylaminophenols and their Nitroso-hydrochlorides.—3-Dimethylaminophenol, 3-di-*n*-propylaminophenol, 3-di-*n*-butylaminophenol, 3-di-*n*-amylaminophenol, 3-di-*n*-hexylaminophenol and their nitroso-hydrochlorides, required in the preparation of benzo(a) phenoxazonium salts, were prepared in exactly the same way as described by Crossley *et al.* (*loc.cit.*) except that alkyl iodides were used for alkylation. The boiling points of the syrupy alkylaminophenols were almost identical with those given in the literature and their identity was confirmed by preparing their nitroso-hydrochlorides which had melting or decomposition points in agreement with the figures recorded in the literature.

5-Monoethylamino-2-nitrosophenol hydrochloride was obtained by the Fischer-Hepp rearrangement (*Ber.*, 1886, 19, 2991) of *N*-nitroso-3-ethylaminophenol, prepared by the nitrosation of 3-ethylaminophenol. Its decomposition point (175°-180°) was also found to be correct.

The nitroso derivatives of 3-di-*n*-butylaminophenol and 3-di-*n*-amylaminophenol could not be isolated, and hence, the orange reaction solutions were directly used in the condensations.

Benzo(a)phenoxazonium Salts

5-β-Hydroxyethylamino-9-dimethylaminobenzo(a)phenoxazonium Chloride (I).—To a suspension of 2-naphthyl(N-β-hydroxyethyl)amine (3.7 g., 0.02 *M*) in 24 c. c. of absolute ethanol were added 5-dimethylamino-2-nitrosophenol hydrochloride (6 g., 0.03 *M*) and 0.5 c.c. of HCl (conc.), and the mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath under stirring for 3 hours. The original orange colour of the reaction mixture gradually darkened, changed to green and ultimately blue. On cooling the solution, dark green lustrous crystals separated out, m.p. 118-20°, yield 4 g.

For the preparation of the picrate, aqueous solution of the dye was basified with ammonium hydroxide (conc.) and extracted with ether. To the dry extract saturated ethereal solution of picric acid (dry) was added till no further precipitation. The picrate was obtained in yellow shining crystals in almost theoretical yield. In view of the sharp

melting point and shining crystalline form of the picrate, further purification by recrystallisation was considered unnecessary, m.p. 184°.

The picrate obtained was identified as (5:9)dipicrate of 5- β -hydroxyethylamino-9-dimethylaminobenzo(a)phenoxazine. [Found: N, 15.38. $C_{26}H_{20}O_2N_3$. ($C_6H_5O_7N_3$)₂ requires N, 15.91 per cent].

5- β -Hydroxyethylamino-9-ethylaminobenzo(a)phenoxazonium Chloride (II).—The condensation was carried out under exactly similar conditions as given in the previous case by treating the naphthylamine derivative (3.7 g., 0.02 M) in 24 c.c. absolute ethanol with 5-ethylamino-2-nitrosophenol hydrochloride (6 g., 0.03 M) in the presence of HCl (conc., 0.5 c.c.).^f In the reaction mixture the same colour changes were observed, and on cooling, a solid of dark bluish green colour separated out. It decomposed above 150°, yield 3.8 g.

The dye was subsequently converted into the picrate, 5- β -hydroxyethylamino-9-ethylaminobenzo(a)phenoxazine (5:9) dipicrate, in the same way from the free base, in green shining crystals, m.p. 205°. [Found: N, 16.20. $C_{26}H_{20}O_2N_3$. ($C_6H_5O_7N_3$)₂ requires N, 15.91 per cent].

5- β -Hydroxyethylamino-9-di-n-propylaminobenzo(a)phenoxazonium Chloride (III).—This condensation was carried out exactly as above with α -naphthylamino compound and 5-di-n-propylamino-2-nitrosophenol hydrochloride. Under similar conditions, shining dark green crystals separated out which melted sharply at 152°, yield 4.2 g.

The base obtained from the salt was converted into 5- β -hydroxyethylamino-9-di-n-propylaminobenzo(a)phenoxazine (5:9) dipicrate, by the same technique, in bottle-green shining crystals, m.p. 194°. [Found: N, 14.43. $C_{26}H_{26}O_2N_3$. ($C_6H_5O_7N_3$)₂ requires N, 14.85 per cent].

5- β -Hydroxyethylamino-9-di-n-butylaminobenzo(a)phenoxazonium Chloride (IV).—As 5-di-n-butylamino-2-nitrosophenol hydrochloride could not be isolated in the solid state, the orange reaction solution, obtained by the nitrosation of 3-di-n-butylaminophenol (10 g., 0.05 M) was added to a suspension of the naphthylamine derivative (3.7 g., 0.02 M) in 24 c.c. absolute ethanol along with HCl (conc., 0.5 c.c.). By the usual treatment, the mixture turned into a dark green syrup from which the dye could not be separated out even on cooling in the freezing mixture. Slow evaporation of the alcoholic solution ultimately left a dark green mass which could not be worked out and as such the dye could not be characterised.

5- β -Hydroxyethylamino-9-di-n-amylaminobenzo(a)phenoxazonium Chloride (V).—Same difficulty was observed in the isolation of this dye as the entire reaction solution obtained by the nitrosation of 3-di-n-amylaminophenol (12.5 g., 0.05 M) had to be added to naphthylamine derivative (3.7 g., 0.02 M) in 24 c.c. of absolute ethanol containing HCl (conc., 0.5 c.c.). The final reaction mixture was again a dark green syrup. Slow evaporation of the alcoholic solution left a similar dark green mass which could not be identified.

5- β -Hydroxyethylamino-9-di-n-hexylaminobenzo(a)phenoxazonium Chloride (VI).—5-Di-n-hexylamino-2-nitroso hydrochloride (10 g., 0.03 M) was added to a suspension of naphthylamine derivative (3.7 g., 0.02 M) in 24 c.c. absolute ethanol followed, by HCl

(conc., 0.5 c.c.). After refluxing for $3\frac{1}{2}$ hours under stirring, a dark green solution was obtained which afforded a crystalline solid of the same colour on cooling, m.p. above 130° (not sharp), yield 4.5 g.

The picrate was obtained from the dye in the usual way in bottle-green crystals [$5\text{-}\beta\text{-hydroxyethylamino-9-di-}n\text{-hexylaminobenzo (a) phenoxazine 5 : 9\text{-dipicrate}$], m.p. $> 300^\circ$. (Found: N, 13.82. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_5\text{N}_5$. $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N}_3)_2$ requires N, 13.52 per cent).

Aminophenoxazines

2-Chloro-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl was obtained in about 80% yield by treating *2-oxy-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl* (8 g.) with POCl_3 (30 c.c.) and *diethylaniline* (8 c.c.) in the usual way, m.p. 119° .

4-Chloro-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl was obtained from *4-oxy-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl* by treating with the same proportions of POCl_3 and *diethylaniline*, m.p. $150\text{-}51^\circ$.

4-Chloro-3 : 5 : 4'-trinitrodiphenyl was obtained in almost theoretical yield on treatment of *4-oxy-3 : 5 : 4'-trinitrodiphenyl* with POCl_3 and *diethylaniline*, m.p. 171° .

4-Chloro-3 : 5-dinitro-1-tert.-butylbenzene was prepared from *4-oxy-3 : 5-dinitro-1-tert.-butylbenzene*, *diethylaniline* and POCl_3 in the usual way, m.p. $115\text{-}16^\circ$.

(I). *1-Phenyl-3-nitrophenoxazine*.—*o*-Aminophenol (1.5 g.) and *2-chloro-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl* (3.6 g.) were dissolved in 15 c.c. of alcohol and 2*N* sodium acetate solution (6 c.c., approx.) added. The mixture was refluxed under stirring for 5 hours and then 2*N*-NaOH (ca. 10 c.c.) was slowly added to the boiling mixture. The solution turned red and it was boiled for 30 minutes more. On allowing it to cool overnight, a dark brown product separated out, which was washed with dilute NaOH solution, followed by ethanol. Recrystallisation from *o*-xylene yielded fine reddish brown crystals (4 g.), m.p. 212° . (Found: N, 9.56. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires N, 9.21 per cent).

(II). *3-Phenyl-1-nitrophenoxazine*.—*4-Chloro-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl* (3.6 g.), *o*-aminophenol (1.5 g.) in 2*N* sodium acetate (ca. 8 c.c.) and alcohol (15 c.c.) were stirred and heated under reflux for 4 hours. 2*N*-NaOH (ca. 10 c.c.) was then added. The mixture was boiled for half an hour more and set aside overnight. The dark brown solid obtained (3.8 g.), after washing with dilute NaOH solution and alcohol, was recrystallised from toluene in dark brown needles, m.p. 200° . (Found: N, 9.48. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires N, 9.21 per cent).

(III). *3-(4'-Nitrodiphenyl)-1-nitrophenoxazine*.—*4-Chloro-3 : 5 : 4'-trinitrodiphenyl* (4.2 g.), when treated with similar proportions of *o*-aminophenol and NaOH in the medium of alcohol and sodium acetate solution, as described in the previous cases, yielded a brown solid (4.0 g.) which was recrystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. 238° . (Found: N, 12.45. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires N, 12.03 per cent).

(IV). *3-tert.-Butyl-1-nitrophenoxazine* was obtained in the usual way from *4-chloro-3 : 5-dinitro-1-tert.-butylbenzene* (3.3 g.), *o*-aminophenol (1.5 g.), ethyl alcohol (15 c.c.), 2*N* sodium acetate (ca. 8 c.c.) and 2*N*-NaOH (ca. 10 c.c.), as a dark brown powder. It was recrystallised from *o*-xylene in shining dark brown needles, m.p. 170° , yield 4.0 g. (Found: N, 10.10. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires N, 9.85 per cent).

3-Imino-1-phenylphenoxazine (I).—*1-Phenyl-3-nitrophenoxazine* (1 g.), suspended in glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.), was reduced at ordinary temperature by shaking in an

atmosphere of hydrogen (60 lbs. pressure) for 12 hours, using Adams' catalyst (60 mg.). The colorless solution obtained immediately turned red on exposure to air. The solution was filtered, concentrated in vacuo to 10 c.c. and made alkaline with dilute NaOH. The crude base, thus separated, was dissolved in benzene and kept over anhydrous sodium sulphate overnight. On passing dry HCl gas through the benzene solution, the imine hydrochloride separated out (1 g.) which was filtered off, washed with dry benzene and dried in vacuum.

Attempts to remove the small amount of water-insoluble material from the hydrochloride failed, and hence, it was converted into the picrate.

The picrate was easily obtained as a red precipitate by adding a saturated aqueous picric acid solution to a filtered aqueous solution (red) of the imine hydrochloride. Recrystallisation from a mixture of saturated aqueous picric acid and ethanol (3:4) furnished fine red crystals (3-imino-1-phenylphenoxazine picrate), m.p. 195°. (Found: N, 14.25. $C_{18}H_{12}ON_2 \cdot C_6H_2O_7N_3$, requires N, 13.91 per cent).

1-Imino-3-phenylphenoxazine (II').—3-Phenyl-1-nitrophenoxazine (1 g.) was also reduced in the same way, using Adams' catalyst (60 mg.) in the medium of glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) with 60 lbs. initial pressure of hydrogen. The colorless solution thus obtained turned red on exposure. The base, obtained on making the solution alkaline with caustic soda solution, was converted into the hydrochloride (1 g.) by the same process. The imine hydrochloride was quite soluble in water and alcohol but contained some water-insoluble impurity.

Aqueous solution of the imine hydrochloride afforded on treatment with a saturated aqueous picric acid solution, a reddish brown precipitate of 1-imino-3-phenylphenoxazine picrate. It was also recrystallised from a mixture of alcohol and aqueous picric acid, m.p. 180°. (Found: N, 13.82. $C_{18}H_{12}ON_2 \cdot C_6H_2O_7N_3$, requires N, 13.91 per cent).

1:4'-Di-imino-3-phenylphenoxazine (III').—Reduction of 3-(4'-nitrophenyl)-1-nitrophenoxazine was carried out by the same technique. In this case, however, the reduced solution turned green and ultimately deep blue on exposure. The hydrochloride, obtained from the base, contained water-insoluble material as usual. The aqueous solution of the imine hydrochloride was also blue. On adding saturated aqueous picric acid to it, a deep green precipitate of the picrate was obtained, which was recrystallised from a mixture of alcohol and aqueous picric acid, m.p. 182°. (Found: N, 16.0. $C_{18}H_{12}ON_3 \cdot C_6H_2O_7N_3$, requires N, 16.31 per cent).

1-Imino-3-tert.-butylphenoxazine (IV').—3-tert.-Butyl-1-nitrophenoxazine was reduced catalytically by the same procedure, yielding a colorless solution. This solution also turned red on exposure. The base separating, after treatment with dilute NaOH, was converted into its hydrochloride which contained about 33% water-insoluble material. The aqueous extract was therefore concentrated to half the volume before addition of saturated aqueous picric acid. The reddish brown picrate, thus obtained, was recrystallised in the usual way, m.p. 300° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.84. $C_{18}H_{18}ON_2 \cdot C_6H_2O_7N_3$, requires N, 14.55 per cent).